

Tensile properties of electrospun polyacrylonitrile nanofibres: Influence of fibre orientation and stretching

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ABSTRACT

The tensile mechanical properties of electrospun polyacrylonitrile (PAN) nanofibres are generally lower when compared to melt and solution-spun fibres. Whilst electrospinning has been reported extensively, the effect of stretching of aligned nanofibres has not received significant coverage. In the current study, aligned electrospun PAN nanofibres were produced using the Vee-shield technique. The polymer concentration was 12 wt/vol% in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The tensile strength and modulus of the aligned PAN nanofibres were 76.31 ± 3.34 MPa and 4.05 ± 1.17 GPa respectively. This represents a threefold increase over the randomly oriented nanofibres (27.8 ± 1.90 MPa, 0.70 ± 0.22 GPa). Post-stretching (13.3% strain, held for 1, 2 and 4 h) of the aligned nanofibres enhanced the tensile strength by 18.27%. The viscoelastic behaviour of the stretched nanofibres was characterised using the generalised Maxwell model and excellent correlation ($R^2 = 0.96$) was observed between the experimental and predicted datasets. This paper demonstrates that the mechanical properties of electrospun PAN nanofibres can be enhanced through fibre alignment and controlled post-alignment stretching. This technique offers a method for improving the tensile properties of electrospun nanofibres.

1. Introduction

Electrospinning is an ideal technique for producing polymer nanofibres with high surface area-to-volume ratios. This field is advancing rapidly, where complex and multi-material architectures are being created to produce functional materials and devices [1]. This is evident in the development of core-sheath [2], trilayer [3] and Janus nanofibres [4] for targeted drug delivery [5], sensors [6] and smart textiles [7]. The integration of these advanced nanostructures into practical devices will invariably require improved and predictable mechanical properties. Highly aligned nanofibres are the ideal candidate as they can offer superior tensile strength and modulus when compared to their randomly oriented counterparts. Whilst innovation in nanofibre technology continues to grow, consideration of the mechanical properties and viscoelastic behaviour of aligned nanofibre bundles themselves has received limited attention.

In order to address this gap, polyacrylonitrile (PAN) was used in the current study. PAN is a semi-crystalline thermoplastic that is used widely in textiles [8], composites [9], filtration [10], water purification [11], photocatalytic [12,13], bio-medical [14] and energy storage applications [15–17]. PAN is also the predominant precursor that is used

for the production of carbon fibres [18]. The thermal stability [19], chemical resistance [20] and mechanical properties of commercial-grade PAN stem from its relatively high molar mass (150,000 – 230,000 g/mol) [21], crystallinity [22] and the relatively strong intermolecular forces due to the presence of the nitrile groups [23].

Whilst established methods for producing fibres such as melt [24], gel [25] and wet-spinning [26] of PAN, along with cold-drawing, enable the microstructure [27] and mechanical properties [24] of PAN fibres to be controlled, electrospinning offers a unique opportunity to produce fibres with diameters in the nanometre scale. In conventional fibre spinning, the diameter of the fibre is influenced by solution viscosity [28], inner bore of the individual spinnerets [29], extrusion pressure [30], solidification rate [31] and the rotation speed of the haul-off spooler [32]. With reference to electrospinning, a fine polymer jet is ejected from a pendant solvent-rich polymer solution that is maintained at the tip of the spinneret (a hypodermic needle) upon the application of an electrical potential between the spinneret and a grounded electrode. The solution [33], processing [34,35] and environmental conditions [36] can be adjusted to influence the microstructure [37] and the diameter of electrospun fibres [38]. The ejected polymer jet travels in a relatively straight trajectory in relation to the spinneret but then

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undergoes uncontrolled whipping, which leads to considerable stretching. This results in a significant reduction in the diameter where nanometre or micrometre ranges can be obtained [39]. The uncontrolled whipping of the polymer jet during electrospinning has been attributed to factors such as electrostatic repulsion, Coulombic forces, surface tension, solvent evaporation rate and ambient conditions [40–42]. The consequence of the uncontrolled whipping of the polymer jet is that the fibres are deposited in a random manner on the grounded electrode. The whipping action of the polymer jet also enhances the rate of evaporation of the solvent [43]; this leads to the formation of a polymer skin, which aids the retention of the circular cross-section of the fibres whilst and after they are deposited on the grounded electrode [44]. However, the skin will also retard the rate of solvent evaporation from the core. It has been reported that during electrospinning, the whipping of the polymer jet reaches strain rates of 10^4 to 10^6 s⁻¹ [45,46]. This is believed to cause molecular alignment and enhance anisotropy in the fibre [47], and according to simulations, it promotes crystallisation [22,48]. However, a number of studies have noted that the tensile strength and modulus of electrospun PAN nanofibres (and their derived carbon fibres) fall significantly short of those achieved through conventional fibre-forming methods [49–52].

A summary of selected papers that report on the tensile strength of electrospun PAN fibres is presented in Table SM1; relevant data from conventional wet and melt-spinning are also included to highlight the differences in the mechanical properties. With reference to electrospun fibres, enhancements in the mechanical properties can be obtained by enhancing the overall alignment of the fibres. This has been achieved using techniques such as high-speed rotating drums [53], rotating discs [54], rotating mandrels with insulating layers [55], centrifugal alignment methods [56], near-field electrospinning [57], parallel electrodes [58], insulating blocks [59], auxiliary electrodes [60] and magnetic field-assisted collection [61]. A critical assessment of these nanofibre alignment methods was presented in Ref. [44].

Although these methods enable the production of aligned fibres, they are batch-based techniques and the extraction of the fibres, whilst maintaining the tension and fibre orientation, is difficult. In a number of applications, for example, the manufacture of woven fabrics or unidirectional fibre preforms, the production of continuous fibres is a prerequisite. Post-processing techniques such as stretching [62] and annealing [63] have been used to improve molecular orientation [64] and the crystallinity [65]. The integration of fillers [66], reinforcements [67], chemical reaction [68], polymer blending [69] and forming composites [70] have been used to modify the microstructure and to enhance the mechanical properties. A summary of selected publications that consider techniques to enhance the mechanical properties of PAN is presented in SM2.

With reference to processing methods, a number of researchers have observed a correlation between the diameter of electrospun fibres and tensile strength [65,71–73]. An efficient way to decrease the diameter of electrospun fibres is to deploy a rotating mandrel as the grounded electrode, where increasing the rotating speed effectively stretches the fibres [32], and concurrently, a degree of macroscopic fibre alignment is obtained [53]. Northolt et al. found that the relationship between the fibre diameter and tensile strength has been attributed to a statistical decrease in the density of flaws as the volume is decreased [74]. With regard to post-processing subsequent to electrospinning, uniaxial stretching has been used to improve the tensile strength and Young's modulus [75].

The primary attribute contributing to enhanced mechanical properties in smaller-diameter fibres after stretching appears to be the increased molecular orientation of the amorphous regions, as reported in Refs. [76–79]. During stretching or cold-drawing of semi-crystalline polymers, the amorphous regions are said to elongate and orient along the tensile direction [77,79]. Experimental studies combining Raman spectroscopy and small-angle neutron scattering (SANS) revealed that cold-drawing and stretching induce elongation and reorganisation of

amorphous regions. This was evident in vibrational modes observed in Raman spectroscopy and nanoscale structural alignment via SANS. [78]. Overall, the degree of molecular alignment was said to be influenced by factors such as strain rate [76], molecular weight [78], the initial degree of crystallinity [80], chain symmetry [81] and degree of branching [78].

In the current study, the effect of stretching on the tensile strength of electrospun aligned and randomly oriented PAN nanofibres was investigated. The aligned fibres were produced using a novel Vee-shield alignment method [44]. With reference to the production of randomly oriented nanofibres, due attention was paid to producing samples with a uniform thickness and average fibre diameter. The specimens were end-tabbed and tensile tested in accordance with the methodology that was reported previously by the authors [82].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

PAN was purchased from Goodfellow, UK, in powder form, with an average molecular weight of 230,000 g/mol. DMSO with a purity of 99% was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, UK. The PAN solutions were prepared in a 250 mL 3-neck round-bottom flask under reflux. In addition to using a magnetic stirrer to agitate the polymer solution, dry nitrogen gas was bubbled into the liquid at 10 mL/min. The refluxing was carried out for 6 h at 60 °C. The polymer concentration was 12 wt/vol% in DMSO.

2.2. Electrospinning procedure

The PAN/DMSO solution was loaded into a 5 mL syringe and secured within a World Precision Instruments NE-300 liquid dispenser. The solution was delivered through a 20 mm long, flat-tip 25-gauge needle that was connected to the syringe via Masterflex PTFE transfer tubing. The needle, acting as the positive electrode, was connected to a high-voltage DC power supply via a copper ring (0.5 mm ID, 0.8 mm OD, 1 mm thickness). The applied voltage was 14 kV. The environment within the electrospinning chamber was maintained at 55 ± 4 °C and $13 \pm 4\%$ relative humidity. The temperature was regulated using a combination of a Phillips 175 W infrared lamp and a Dimplex portable storage heater. The humidity was maintained through the use of 50 g of pre-dried silica gel. A digital thermometer-hygrometer (RS Pro, UK) was used to monitor the temperature and relative humidity continuously. With reference to the conventional electrospinning setup, a grounded circular copper electrode (10 cm diameter, 0.9 mm thickness) served as the counter-electrode.

Randomly oriented fibres: The experimental setup for the production of randomly oriented nanofibre mats is shown in Fig. 1. A quasi-

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the rotating mandrel set-up for producing randomly oriented PAN nanofibres: (i) solution dispensing unit; (ii) syringe; (iii) electrospinning chamber; (iv) PTFE tube; (v) positive terminal; (vi) needle; (vii) infrared lamp; (viii) rotating mandrel; (ix) high-voltage power supply; (x) electric motor; (xi) computer; and (xii) silica gel. The insert in the top right corner shows a transparent view of the ground connection between the wire (green) and the inner surface of the mandrel.

static rotating mandrel was used as samples produced using a conventional static grounded electrode generally result in a gradient in the thickness from the centre to the outer perimeter. The rotating mandrel used in the current study was computer-controlled and it had a horizontal traverse of 50 mm. This approach enabled the production of electrospun randomly oriented nanofibres with a relatively uniform thickness. The grounded aluminium mandrel had a diameter of 10 cm and a length of 25 cm, and its rotation rate was set at 50 rpm. The mandrel was grounded using a copper wire that was in contact with the inner surface of the mandrel as illustrated in Fig. 1. The traverse distance and the speed were set at 100 mm and 20 mm/min respectively. The electrospinning was carried out for 1 h, with a solution feed rate of 0.3 mL/h. A layer of aluminium foil was wrapped tightly around the mandrel to enable easy removal of the electrospun fibres.

Aligned nanofibres: The custom-designed grounded collector, referred to as the Vee-shield collector, was used to produce aligned PAN nanofibres. This set-up was previously described by the authors [44] and only a brief description is presented here. A schematic illustration of the set-up of the Vee-shield method is shown in Fig. 2 (a). An expanded view of the Vee-shield assembly is shown in Fig. 2 (b). It was constructed from a sheet of PTFE (Direct Plastic, UK) with dimensions of 10 cm width, 25 cm length, and 3 mm thickness (item xi); the angles of the Vee-shield were set at 65° in relation to the vertical plane. The flat section of the Vee-shield (item xii) was 6 mm wide and 100 mm long. A black craft paper (80 gsm, Ryman, UK) strip with dimensions of 6 mm \times 100 mm \times 0.1 mm was used as the static substrate for collecting aligned nanofibres. The grounded electrode is represented by item xiii. The distance between the needle tip and the paper substrate's centre point was set at 100 mm. The fibre alignment direction is shown by the arrow in Fig. 2 (b). The solution feed rate was maintained at 0.01 mL/h, and each aligned nanofibre sample was spun for 1 h in order to maintain a similar weight and thickness as the samples with the randomly oriented fibres.

2.3. Preparation of tensile test specimens

Following electrospinning of the randomly oriented fibres, the aluminium foil substrate was detached from the mandrel. A central strip, measuring 6 mm \times 315 mm, was cut from the foil using an 18 mm rotary cutter (Olfa, UK). The rotary cutter was chosen over traditional blades or scissors to minimise crinkling of the aluminium foil and to reduce deformation of the PAN fibres whilst sectioning. This large strip was then sectioned into four, each 6 mm wide and 65 mm long. In the case of the aligned nanofibres, prior to removal from the Vee-shield collector, the edges of the 6 mm \times 65 mm paper substrate were cut using the 18 mm rotary cutter. This pre-cutting step was necessary to preserve the spatial orientation of the nanofibres from being dislodged by the fibres that were deposited outside the desired area, as they were removed. The randomly oriented and aligned nanofibre strips were then separated

Fig. 2. Schematic illustrations of: (a) the custom-designed Vee-shield grounded electrode configuration for producing aligned nanofibres; and (b) an enlarged schematic illustration of the Vee-shield collector. See text for details.

carefully from their respective substrates and transferred to pre-prepared 40 mm \times 70 mm paper frames. This mounting procedure, including details of the methodology for preparing the frame was described in a previous publication [82]. In summary, the electrospun mat was sectioned using a rotary cutter to length and width corresponding to 6 and 65 mm, respectively. The sample was bonded to a polyethylene terephthalate (PET) window frame of dimension 30 mm \times 20 mm with an inner frame cut by a die puncher with 15 mm \times 15 mm, using a UV-curable adhesive. Due care and attention were paid to ensuring that the adhesive did not wick into the gauge length of the tensile test specimen. Prior to tensile testing, the fibre samples were dried in a vacuum oven at 120°C and 1 mbar for 6 h. The mounted fibre arrays were then secured to a Teflon-coated metal tray using heat-resistant tape (3M, 8992, UK), where minimal manual tension was applied to the test specimen.

Tensile test specimens were prepared according to the method detailed in a previous publication [82]. A UV-curable resin (NOA 68, Norland, US) was used as the end-tab adhesive. The specimens were fabricated with a gauge length of 15 mm and a width of 6 mm. Due care and attention was given to ensure that the end-tab adhesive did not wick into the gauge length. Ten randomly oriented and twenty aligned nanofibre specimens were prepared and end-tabbed.

2.4. Tensile testing

2.4.1. Tensile testing to failure

The tensile properties of the nanofibre arrays were determined using an Instron 5566 universal testing machine equipped with a 10 N load cell. With regard to gripping the nanofibre tensile samples, a pair of fibre filament micro tensile grips (2711-006 series, Instron, UK), with adjustable clamping force and self-aligning hard rubber-coated faces (36 mm² gripped area, 5 N maximum load capacity) were used. Tests were conducted in a temperature and humidity-controlled laboratory at $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $20 \pm 4\%$ RH. Prior to tensile testing, the gauge length and width of each specimen (within the window frame) were measured five times from photographs using ImageJ software, and the average values were recorded. The thickness was measured using a Mitutoyo Digimatic micrometre (model 293-344-30, IP65; 0.001 mm; ratchet-thimble, 7–12 N). In order to prevent torsional damage during rotation of the spindle, a 0.05 mm stainless steel feeler gauge was placed on the spindle side; the instrument was zeroed with the shim in place (0.05 mm offset). Therefore, the reported values correspond to the specimen thickness. Five measurements were taken from each specimen, and the average value was reported. The specimens were mounted carefully in the grips to ensure that the fibre alignment was parallel to the loading direction. Before starting the test, the sides of the paper frame were cut, ensuring that only the nanofibres were subjected to the applied load via the end-tabs. After zeroing the load and displacement, tests were performed at a cross-head displacement rate of 1 mm/min, and load-displacement data were recorded using Bluehill 3® software. A minimum of ten replicate tests were conducted for each condition: randomly oriented; aligned; and aligned pre-stressed specimens.

2.4.2. Stretching – stress relaxation

The stretching of the aligned electrospun nanofibres were carried out to strain of 13.3%, and held for 1, 2 and 4 h. After this hold-period, the samples were tensile tested to failure. The tensile tests were carried out at $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

2.5. Scanning electron microscopy

The surface morphology of fibres were inspected using a Hitachi TM3030plus tabletop scanning electron microscope (SEM). The instrument was operated at 15 kV and the working distance was 8 μm . Sections of the electrospun fibre mats were mounted onto a circular aluminium SEM stub using double-sided conductive carbon adhesive tape. The

fibres were sputter-coated with gold/palladium alloy for 3 min using an Emscope SC 500 vacuum sputter-coater to render the sample conductive.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Electrospinning of PAN nanofibres and sample preparation

The electrospinning processing parameters summarised in Table 1 enabled the production of electrospun fibres that were bead-free, unfused, continuous, and of a circular cross-section. Whilst a conventional flat grounded electrode can be used to produce randomly oriented nanofibre mats, it is not ideal for the production of tensile test specimens because the thickness of the mat decreases from the centre (below the spinneret) to the outer perimeter [82]. Therefore, a rotating drum with the high-voltage electrode, as shown in Fig. 1, was used. This enabled the production of tensile test specimens with a relatively uniform thickness of $6 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$. In the case when a static grounded electrode was used, the variation in the thickness was $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ from the centre to the outer perimeter. The processing parameters for producing the electrospun randomly oriented and aligned fibres are summarised in Table 1.

It was reported in Ref. [44] that introducing the PTFE Vee-shield was seen to have a significant influence on the electrical potential, electric field strength, current density and current density vector. In practical terms, the PTFE Vee-shield confines the electric potential between the needle and the ends of the grounded collector. In the current case, the ejected polymer jet oscillated primarily between the exposed ends of the grounded electrode. Therefore, aligned fibres were deposited along the length of the substrate. The methodology for continuous spooling of the aligned fibres was reported in Ref. [44]. In order to render the current paper self-contained, an overview of the COMSOL modelling is presented in the Supplementary Materials section (see SM3). The modelling presented in SM3 also explains as to why it was necessary to change the liquid dispensing rate for the Vee-shield method when compared to the conventional grounded electrode.

Regarding the specific advantages of the Vee-shield electrospinning technique, the issues relating to advantages, scalability and cost-effectiveness are as follows:

Continuous production & spooling: In the case of conventional techniques for producing aligned electro-spun nanofibres, for example, rotating mandrels or parallel electrodes, they are typically batch-based production methods. Furthermore, the fibre lengths are relatively short. The Vee-shield method enables the continuous production and spooling of aligned nano-fibre arrays. In other words, continuous tapes can be produced [44].

Post-processing: Once the aligned fibres are produced, it is possible to use secondary electrospinning or spraying units to deposit additional materials of different compositions; alternatively, secondary heating and cooling can be used to influence removal of the solvent and the crystallinity. Furthermore, *in situ* stretching of the nanofibre arrays can be enabled by using multiple haul-off units. A major advantage of the Vee-shield technique is the easy extraction of the aligned nanofibres without causing any damage, loss of tension and alignment.

Quasi-isotropic and novel fibre architectures: As demonstrated in Ref. [44], the Vee-shield method allows the production of quasi-isotropic fibre arrays (e.g., 0° , 90° , $+45^\circ$, -45°) preforms by

rotating the shield, without the need for complex machinery or manual layout. The Vee-shield technique is capable of being adapted for some of the recent innovations in electrospinning, such as co- [83] and tri-axial [84] electrospinning.

Scale-up: Whilst this was not addressed in the current manuscript, scale-up of the equipment can be achieved using multiple spinnerets, where the width of the substrate on which the fibres are deposited can be increased.

The density of the electrospun fibres was measured using helium pycnometry and was determined to be $\sim 1.184 \text{ g/cm}^3$. This is similar to that of bulk polyacrylonitrile (PAN) [85].

Fig. 3 (a and b) show SEM micrographs of the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres respectively; the corresponding fibre diameter distributions are shown in Fig. 3 (c and d) respectively. With reference to the diameter distribution plot for the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres shown in Fig. 3 (c and d), the average diameters from measuring 300 individual fibres from 3 micrographs for each dataset were 367.4 and 385.5 nm respectively, and the standard deviation was 50.3 nm and 80.4 nm respectively. In the initial statistical analysis of the fibre diameters, the dataset was ranked (lowest to highest) and filtered (every 10 points) from 300 to 31 in order to perform the T-test. However, given the significantly larger standard deviation for the aligned fibres, the full 300 datasets were also used. The conclusion from this analysis was that the diameters for the randomly oriented and aligned fibres cannot be assumed to be the same if the full dataset of 300 is used. This is because the aligned fibres had a tail in the distribution where larger diameter fibres were present. The details of the statistical analysis are presented in SM4.

The broader fibre diameter distribution observed in the aligned PAN nanofibres may be attributed to the use of the Vee-shield collector, which incorporates a dielectric material that reduces the effective electric field strength. This reduction in field intensity was shown experimentally and through simulations [44] to reduce the whipping of the polymer jet, and this is attributed to the observed larger diameter fibres. Additionally, the feed-rate for the aligned fibres was set at a lower value (0.01 mL/h). This was necessary to maintain a stable Taylor cone as a consequence of the weaker electric field when the Vee-shield was used [44], see SM3. Using higher feed rates under these processing conditions were observed to destabilise the polymer jet and lead to dripping and the formation of non-uniform fibres. The above-mentioned factors contributed to the observed increase in variation in fibre diameter for the aligned samples.

3.2. Tensile testing

3.2.1. Randomly oriented PAN nanofibres

Fig. 4 shows a typical stress-strain curve for the randomly oriented PAN nanofibres. The macroscopic deformation modes were photographed periodically during tensile loading and are superimposed in Fig. 4; the correlation between specific numerical codes inscribed on the stress-strain plot are reproduced on the photographs. The macroscopic appearance of the test specimen at the start of the tensile test is shown in Fig. 4 (i). The dotted red line has been superimposed to illustrate the linear portion of the stress/strain plot. The appearance of the sample at the yield stress is shown in Fig. 4 (ii). Plastic deformation is prevalent beyond point-iii. The decrease in the observed stress between points-iii to iv is likely due to the onset of yielding of the fibres that are bonded at

Table 1

Summary of the processing parameters that were used for producing bead-free and unfused electrospun PAN fibres for tensile testing.

Fibre Type	Collector	Needle (gauge)	Applied Voltage (kV)	Feeding Rate (mL/hour)	Working Distance (cm)	Sample Spinning Time (minutes)	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Relative Humidity (%)
Random	Rotating mandrel (50 RPM)	25	14	0.3	10	60	55 ± 4	13 ± 4
Aligned	Vee-shield	25	14	0.01	10	60	55 ± 4	13 ± 4

Fig. 3. (a-d): (a and b) Micrographs showing the morphologies of the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres, respectively; and (c and d) Fibre diameter distribution plots for the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres.

Fig. 4. Typical stress-strain curve for the randomly oriented PAN nanofibres. The inscribed numbers on the stress/strain plot correlate with the coding on the photographs showing the macroscopic appearance of the test specimen.

each end of the end-tabs. Close inspection of the specimen showed a degree of “creasing” caused by the non-uniform loading as a consequence of the randomly oriented fibres. These creases were observed to diminish and eventually disappear as the sample was stretched; this implies that the randomly oriented fibres are drawn to the principal loading direction. Beyond this point (Fig. 4 (ii)), the sample was observed to extend for a short period without any increase in the stress. Fig. 4 (iii) shows the apparent necking of the sample. However, it is proposed that, where the fibres are oriented randomly relative to the principal loading direction, this is not conventional necking that is observed when tensile testing solid monolithic polymers. The reduction in the cross-section is due to Poisson's contraction and the extensive realignment of the off-axis fibres during tensile loading. Since there is

significant entanglement of the randomly oriented fibres within the gauge length, these fibres attempt to realign to the loading direction. Further loading resulted in the drawing and extension of the necked region, as seen in Fig. 4 (v). This region is relatively linear up to about 45% strain, after which there is a change in the slope before the failure stress is reached point-vi, where the strain is approximately 64%. Beyond the peak stress (point-vi), the fracture of filaments starts and failure was observed in the majority of the cases. A number of periodic load-drops were observed past the peak stress (point-vi). In the majority of the cases, the macroscopic failure zone was just below the end-tabbed region. The average ultimate failure strain for the randomly oriented PAN nanofibres was 83%.

Evidence for the induced macroscopic alignment of the randomly

oriented PAN nanofibres during the tensile test is shown in Fig. 5 (a–f). Since the nanofibres within the gauge length region are not pinned (unlike those bonded within the end-tab regions), they are relatively free to re-orientate towards the principal tensile load direction. These samples were prepared as described previously, where each tensile specimen was loaded to approximate points marked (i, ii, iv–vii) on the stress/strain plot and secured at these extensions using a secondary clamping device. This assembly was transferred to the SEM, where the relative spatial orientation of the fibres was retained. The secondary clamping method used in generating the data for Fig. 5 (a–f) meant that stress relaxation in the fibres would not have contributed to any major changes in the orientation of the fibres. With reference to Fig. 5 (a–f), the corresponding average fibre orientation angles for this dataset are shown in Fig. 5 (a'–e'). The relative orientation of the fibres in Fig. 5 (a–e) was estimated by superimposing a window of 300 x 300 pixels on the micrographs. The relative orientation of the fibres was measured relative to a vertical reference line that was drawn on the centre of each micrograph. Fibre orientation angles were measured relative to the blue vertical reference arrow line and ranged from -90° to $+90^\circ$, with clockwise tilting assigned positive values and counterclockwise tilting assigned negative values.

Fig. 5 (a'–e') shows the distribution of the fibre angles as a function of applied tensile load on the randomly oriented PAN nanofibres. The

applied strain levels for a'–e' were 0%, 2%, 17%, 40% and 65% respectively. On inspecting Fig. 5 (a'–e'), the angular distribution of the nanofibres decreases from Fig. 5 (a'–e'). For example, the % of fibres between -30° and $+30^\circ$ in Fig. 5 (a'–f) is 36%, 52%, 59%, 67% and 73%. This provides evidence that the randomly oriented fibres within the gauge length attempt to realign to during tensile loading.

In Fig. 5 (f), it is acknowledged that the fibres would recoil upon fracture, but the relative orientation of the nanofibres above the primary fracture zone have retained their spatial orientation. This is probably because of the significant entanglement of the random fibres as they are stretched and drawn during tensile loading. The average fibre diameter of the randomly oriented nanofibre before and after tensile testing decreased from 367.4 nm to 334.0 nm. The standard deviation increased from 50.3 nm to 54.4 nm, which is probably due to the fact that the fibres were oriented randomly at the start of the tensile test.

3.2.2. Tensile testing of aligned PAN nanofibres

Fig. 6 (a) shows a typical stress-strain curve for the aligned PAN nanofibres. As in the previous case, a video was recorded during the tensile tests and relevant photographs were extracted to enable correlation between the observed macroscopic deformation and the applied tensile stress.

The observed macroscopic tensile failure modes for the aligned PAN

Fig. 5. (a–f) Micrographs showing the re-orientation of the randomly oriented nanofibres during tensile loading to failure. The corresponding angular distribution of the fibres are shown in Fig. 5 (a'–e'). The blue arrows show the tensile loading direction.

Fig. 5. (a'-e') Distribution of the fibre angles for the micrographs shown in Fig. 5(a-e).

Fig. 6 (a). Typical stress-strain curve of aligned PAN nanofibres.

nanofibres were different to those observed for the randomly oriented fibres. With reference to Fig. 6 (a), point-i represents the elastic region. From the point of deviation of linearity in the stress/strain plot, increasing Poisson's contraction was observed all the way along point-ii to point-iii. After point-iii, relatively small clusters of fibres were observed to fracture and this was recorded as a dark line on the sample as the light is transmitted through the sample. The dimensions of the dark regions increased with increasing applied load as seen at point-v. After this region, the failure of the fibres was rapid, as represented by the loss of load-carrying ability of the oriented fibre array. The apparent surface crinkles that were seen in the randomly oriented fibres were not

observed in any of the aligned fibres.

The relative differences in the behaviour of the aligned (Fig. 6 (a)) and that of the randomly oriented nanofibres (Fig. 4) can be seen in the combined plot shown in Fig. 6 (b). The improved tensile strength and the Young's modulus is readily apparent for the aligned nanofibres. The aligned fibres are loaded more uniformly and they attain their maximum load-bearing capacity rapidly when compared to the randomly oriented fibres. Fig. 6 (b) also supports the evidence presented in Fig. 5(a-f), where reorientation of the randomly oriented fibres as a function of displacement during tensile loading.

Fig. 6 (b). Combined stress/stain plot for the electrospun aligned and randomly oriented PAN nanofibres.

In contrast to the observed failure mode shown in Fig. 5 (f) for the randomly oriented nanofibres, a brittle-like failure mode for the aligned fibre is shown in Fig. 7. The fibre density is significantly higher in the aligned fibres. The brittle-like failure mode seen in Fig. 7 is attributed to the higher efficiency of the aligned fibres in carrying the applied load as opposed to attempting to realign themselves towards the loading direction observed for the randomly oriented fibres.

Table 2 presents a summary of the tensile properties of the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres. As expected, the aligned PAN nanofibres have higher ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus than randomly oriented PAN nanofibres. The high UTS and Young's modulus of the aligned PAN nanofibres may be attributed to the higher degree of alignment and the lower inter-filament intrinsic porosity. The alignment of the nanofibres was calculated using SEM micrographs and ImageJ software as described in the previous section. As seen in Fig. 8, the aligned PAN nanofibres are oriented close to 0°.

3.2.3. Viscoelastic response of aligned PAN nanofibres

The viscoelastic response of the aligned PAN nanofibres was investigated by performing tensile stress relaxation as shown in Fig. 9. The aligned PAN nanofibres were subjected to a 2 mm extension (strain of 13.3%) for 1, 2 and 4 h. This applied strain is close to the strain at the UTS, i.e. $10.43\% \pm 0.94\%$.

A generalised Maxwell model (also called Maxwell-Wiechert model [86] or Prony series) was used to characterise the relaxation response of the aligned PAN nanofibres. The constitutive relationship for the generalised Maxwell model with N chains is:

$$\sigma(t) = E(t) \cdot \epsilon_0 \quad (1)$$

$$E(t) = E_e + \sum_i^{N-1} E_i \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau_i}\right) \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma(t)$ is the observed stress response at time t of the tensile test (see Fig. 10), ϵ_0 is the held strain, $E(t)$ is the relaxation modulus as a function of the equilibrium modulus E_e and moduli E_i 's for particular relaxation. Time constant for particular relaxation are represented by τ_i 's. The generalised Maxwell model with 3 chains was used to study the viscoelastic response for aligned PAN nanofibres.

$$E(t) = E_e + E_1 \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau_1}\right) + E_2 \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau_2}\right) \quad (3)$$

Fig. 7. Micrograph showing the brittle-like failure of the aligned PAN nanofibres.

Table 2

Summary of the tensile properties of the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres.

Parameter	Randomly oriented PAN nanofibres	Aligned PAN nanofibres
UTS, MPa	27.8 ± 1.90	76.31 ± 3.34
Young's modulus, GPa	0.70 ± 0.22	4.05 ± 1.17
Strain at UTS, %	77.42 ± 6.90	10.43 ± 0.94
Failure strain, %	98.36 ± 9.03	23.26 ± 1.46
Intrinsic porosity, %	72.98 ± 2.77	54.6 ± 0.5

Fig. 8. Degree of orientation for the randomly oriented and aligned PAN nanofibres.

For the Maxwell model for the stress relaxation test at 13.3%:

$$E(t) = 0.29 + 0.10 \exp\left(\frac{-t}{100}\right) + 0.10 \exp\left(\frac{-t}{2200}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$E(t) = 0.29 + 0.10 \left(\exp\left(\frac{-t}{100}\right) + \exp\left(\frac{-t}{2200}\right) \right) \quad (5)$$

The results from the viscoelastic model were in good agreement to those of measured data with high correlation value R^2 of 0.96 (for 13.3% holding-strain); see Fig. 11.

Table 3 shows a comparison of the mechanical properties before and after the stress relaxation experiments. It shows that the UTS and the failure strain at the UTS for the aligned PAN nanofibres after relaxation are higher than those before relaxation. This demonstrates that stretching the nanofibres after production can be used as a viable technique to increase the tensile mechanical properties. However, the breaking strains of aligned PAN nanofibres after relaxation are lower than those before relaxation. Statistical analyses were carried out on the tensile data using the T-test and the results are shown in Table 4. The analysis confirms that the UTS and the Young's moduli before and after stretching are significantly different.

Statistical analysis was also carried out to establish if the relaxation times (after holding for 1, 2 and 4 h) had any effect on the UTS, strain at UTS, and breaking strain. The P-values summarised in Table 5 show that they are higher than 0.05 for the F-test and therefore, it can be concluded that the data sets are not statistically significant for the different stress hold periods.

Wan and Ko [87] investigated the relationship between the tensile properties of an individual nanofibre and that of nanofibre assemblies

Fig. 9. A typical stress/strain plot for the stress relaxation experiments that were conducted at an applied strain of 13.3% for (a) 1, (b) 2 and (c) 4 h respectively.

through geometric analysis. They found that the tensile strength of a

randomly oriented nanofibre mat was a function of fibre packing density (porosity), test specimen dimension (width-to-length ratio), and the tensile strength of a single nanofibre. They developed a model to calculate the tensile strength of aligned nanofibres:

$$\sigma = \frac{(1 - P) [(1 + k^2) \cdot \text{artg}(k) + k]^2}{2\pi k(1 + k^2)^{3/2}} \sigma_f \tag{7}$$

where, σ and σ_f are the UTS of the nanofibre assemblies and single nanofibre respectively. The packing density or porosity of nanofibre assemblies is labelled as P , and K is the ratio of width-to-length of the tensile specimen. Equation (7) is rearranged to calculate the UTS of the nanofibres based on the tensile strength data of the randomly aligned nanofibres.

$$\sigma_f = \frac{2\pi k(1 + k^2)^{3/2}}{(1 - P) [(1 + k^2) \cdot \text{artg}(k) + k]^2} \sigma \tag{8}$$

The tensile strength of single PAN nanofibre is calculated from the tensile strength or UTS of aligned PAN nanofibres and the packing density (porosity) listed in Table 2. The tensile strength of a single PAN nanofibre before and after stretching are 696.70 ± 30.55 MPa and 812.88 ± 55.93 MPa, respectively.

The tensile strength for a single ultra-high molecular weight PAN fibre was reported to be 826 ± 129 MPa [21], and 550 ± 60 MPa for commercial-grade PAN [88], respectively. From the statistical analysis, it is concluded that the tensile strengths of stretched, aligned single PAN nanofibres are not significantly different than those of ultra-high-molecular weight PAN. However, the tensile strength of the unstretched aligned single PAN nanofibres are significantly lower than those of ultra-high-molecular-weight PAN.

4. Conclusion

Highly aligned PAN nanofibres were produced using the Vee-shield alignment method. The tensile properties of the aligned nanofibres (76.3 ± 3.3 MPa tensile strength, 4.05 ± 1.17 GPa modulus) were significantly superior when compared with the randomly oriented nanofibres (27.8 ± 1.9 MPa tensile strength, 0.70 ± 0.22 GPa modulus). Post-production stretching increased the tensile strength further by an average of $18.3\% \pm 8.5\%$. Stress-relaxation experiments on the aligned bundles showed behaviour consistent with the Maxwell-Wiechert viscoelastic model, which predicted the experimental response accurately. These results have vindicated the research hypotheses: (i) the fabrication of mechanically robust and aligned nanofibre bundles, along

Fig. 10. Tensile stress during the stress relaxation for 4 h.

Fig. 11. Stiffness during stress relaxation, including the viscoelastic model.

Table 3

Summary of the mechanical properties after the stress relaxation experiments.

No.	Parameters	Aligned PAN nanofibres		Aligned PAN nanofibres after stress relaxation		
		Initial		1 h	2 h	4 h
1	UTS, MPa	76.71 ± 3.34		86.69 ± 3.33	86.61 ± 6.31	90.25 ± 5.53
2	Strain at UTS, %	10.43 ± 0.94		15.03 ± 0.48	15.34 ± 0.76	15.25 ± 0.21
3	Failure strain, %	23.26 ± 1.46		19.36 ± 2.06	20.46 ± 0.73	21.01 ± 0.87

Table 4

Summary of the T-test results for the tensile properties of aligned PAN nanofibres before and after relaxation.

No	Parameters	T-test of aligned PAN nanofibres after and before (initial) relaxation					
		1 h		2 h		4 h	
		P-value	Remarks	P-value	Remarks	P-value	Remarks
1	UTS, MPa	0.010	Significantly different	0.037	Significantly different	0.011	Significantly different
2	Strain at UTS, %	<0.000	Significantly different	<0.000	Significantly different	<0.000	Significantly different
3	Failure strain, %	0.028	Significantly different	0.021	Significantly different	0.041	Significantly different

Table 5

Summary of the F-test results for the aligned PAN nanofibres that were initially stretched to 13.3% and held for 1, 2 and 4 h.

No.	Parameters	P-Value	Remarks
1	UTS, MPa	0.6434	Not significantly different.
2	Strain at UTS, %	0.7789	Not significantly different.
3	Failure strain, %	0.3780	Not significantly different.

with effective end-tapping, will enable efficient load-transfer to the nanofibres; and (ii) the application of post-production stretching can be used to further enhance the tensile strength and modulus. With reference to future research, the Vee-shield setup with its continuous spooling capability, is an ideal platform to enable simultaneous alignment of the electrospun fibres during deposition, and *in situ* stretching, into a single continuous manufacturing process. This integrated approach will be used to study other polymer systems to tailor the mechanical properties for applications such as sensors, electrodes, tissue engineering scaffolds and high-performance composites.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Siheng Shao: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation,

Conceptualization. **Surya D. Pandita:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Boru An:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Gerard F. Fernando:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymeresting.2026.109105>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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